

ISic3307

I.Sicily inscription 3307

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 550

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]↓[---]

2. [---]cit M[---]

3. (vac.unknown)

4. [---r]equiesci[t---]

5. [---]EDISA[---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493992

EDR 138676

EDCS 22200414

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 220

Libertini, G 1931. Miscellanea epigrafica. *Archivio Storico per la Sicilia Orientale*. 27: 39-53. At 48 no.3 fr.2 = Libertini (1981) 98 no.3 fr.2

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 370 n.2 =
Libertini (1981) 113

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.421

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